

TEACHING THE LIFE AND WORK OF A SHEPHERD USING INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Abstract: this article provides relevant interactive methods, instructions and recommendations for teaching and learning Cholpon's life and work using modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods in literature classes in secondary schools.

Keywords: study, novel-dialogue, drama, method, novel, When numbers speak, Chala letter text.

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Every trainer should feel from the bottom of his heart that "...in order to achieve our great country and our great future, we need to educate intelligent, enlightened people who are proud of their past, great values, nation and believe in the future." The science of literature will help us to ensure that it reaches the students quickly and easily. Because the main task of literature is education. This is the real essence of studying the lives and activities of great figures who can be an example to people with their personality and works, and who share the light of enlightenment with them.

"Studying the writer's life and creative activity helps to determine his worldview. This prepares the ground for giving him a proper assessment." Sometimes we come across views that it is not necessary to study the lives of writers and poets. However, collecting facts about the life of writers and poets should be considered as a real "black work" of science. The reason is that such works are important not only for observing the progress of a concrete creator as a person and an artist or for the correct interpretation of the creative history of a concrete work, but also for elucidating a number of universal aesthetic problems such as the psychology of creativity, the relationship between the creator and society. Information about the writer's life can be obtained from the biographies written by him, from contemporaries, peers, teachers or students, acquaintances and fans of the writer, or from written sources.

Abdulhamid Suleiman's son Cholpon was born in 1897 in Qatorterak quarter of Andijan city. The son of his father, Sulaymonqul Mullah Muhammad Yunus, was one of the prominent people of Andijan and was engaged in trade. He was considered one of the educated people of his time, and he himself wrote poems.

There is information that at that time, the future poet's father compiled a collection of comic poems he had written.

Cholpon's mother, Aysha Aya, although not very educated, had a great influence on her son's creativity. After all, he was well aware of the inexhaustible treasure of folk songs and tales.

Abdulhamid studied at the old school. When the time came, he studied at Andijan and Tashkent madrasas. Suleimankul, who met the demands of the times, also educated his son in a Russian-Tuzem school. The future poet became an educated person who knows the Uzbek, Turkish, Persian, Arabic, Russian languages and literature in these languages thoroughly due to his regular training and natural talent. Due to constant study and strong talent, Abdulhamid began to create before he was sixteen years old. His stories and poems created during this period were published in the newspapers of the Turkestan region.

The extent of the artist's talent is measured by the extent of his love for his people. Great talent often consists of great love. Even in the first works of Cholpon, the boundless love for the people of Turkistan, who were oppressed by the invaders, was clearly visible. He wanted to see his people free and happy. For this, he believed that people should be awakened from the slumber of ignorance and enjoy enlightenment and science. At the same time, the Russian chieftains also knew that they would not allow the nation to become enlightened. It was clear to the poet that there can be no enlightenment without will, and no will without enlightenment. Therefore, Cholpon looked with great hope at the revolution that took place in Russia in February 1917. But this revolution did not give real freedom to Turkestan. Because freedom is not a gift given by another person, class, or nation, but a blessing to be won through struggle. The coup that took place in October of the same year extinguished the last hopes of the poet. Reflecting the plight of the people oppressed by national oppression and the desire to save the people from such a situation became the main direction of Cholpon's work.

In the ancient Uzbek poetry with thousands of years of tradition, Cholpon searched for his own path and was unlike anyone else's, with his sincerity, attractiveness, impressiveness, and the color of his emotions. was able to create a unique poetic world. Today's Uzbek literary language is largely influenced by Cholpon's poems.

Cholpon is also the author of the first Uzbek novel-dialogue called "Night and Day" in addition to his unique poetic discoveries. Unfortunately, according to the memories of his contemporaries, the manuscript of the second book of the novel was destroyed during the imprisonment of Chol Pon and has not been found until now. The first book "Yesterday" was republished in the years of ownership and was

evaluated by many readers as a work on the level of Abdulla Qadiri's novel "Otkan kunlar".

Cholpon's drama "Yorkhinoy" created in 1921 has not lost its influence in terms of artistic appeal.

Abdulhamid Cholpon also did important work in introducing Uzbek students to masterpieces of world literature. His translations of the works of famous writers such as Shakespeare, Blok, Gorky, Thakur became important in the formation of the spirituality of our people.

Cholpon was a creator who made truth and honesty his faith. For this reason, the rulers who claimed national tyranny as national equality did not like his work. They asked the poet to sing that the people are living happily, freely and freely. Cholpan, a singer of truth and a child of freedom, could not do this. That is why they declared him a nationalist and an enemy of the people he loved and sacrificed his life for. The poet was imprisoned on July 14, 1937. The great Uzbek poet was shot on October 4, 1938 in one of the isolated places near Tashkent after long tortures and insults. The terrible thing is that the court decision sentencing Cholpon to death was issued on October 5, 1938. The enemies were in a hurry to destroy the real children of our people as soon as possible, to deprive people of the springs of spirituality.

Samples of Cholpon's work were hidden from students for a long time. Because the Shura system was not interested in studying the work of a brave poet who spoke the truth. But the truth cannot be hidden forever. There is no way to hide the age. Cholpon, as a bright star of Uzbek poetry, tore the veil of passing clouds and shone again in the sky of national poetry.

The 7th grade literature textbook contains information about the life and work of Cholpon. Taking into account the data and time, it is advisable to use the following methods in the lesson.

1. "When numbers speak" method. In this method, the years of Cholpan's life and work given in the textbook are written with numbers. The students in the group write down the events of the given years. This method helps students to think quickly, give clear answers, work in groups, and strengthen their memory.

1. "WHEN THE NUMBERS TALK"

"RAQAMLAR SO'ZLAGANDA"

2. "Unfinished letter text" method. We use this method to strengthen students' theoretical knowledge. For this method, exactly one text is selected. Based on the topic, we chose the theoretical text given about the novel "Night and Day" by Cholpon. Students complete the sentences by putting the necessary words in the blank spaces in the text. This method tests students' ingenuity, resourcefulness, and responsiveness. After listening to the given information, the teacher enriches the students' theoretical knowledge.

"NIGHT AND DAY"

Cholpon's unique poem, in addition to discoveries, is the so-called "night and day" of the Uzbek novel-dialogue is also The work is regarded by many readers as a work on the level of Abdullah 's "The Past Days" took The work was written in-.....-years.

"NIGHT AND DAY"

Cholpon is the author of the first Uzbek novel-dialogue called "night and day" in addition to his unique poems. The work was evaluated by many readers as a work at the level of Abdulla Qadiri's novel "Otkan Kunlar". The work was written in 1935-1936.

So, no matter what genres and topics fiction literature is written in, the main goal expected from it is to educate a person. From this point of view, Cholpon's work has a unique moral, educational and spiritual significance. The general spirit of these works is aimed at educating a person in the spirit of perfection and patriotism.

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